

CodeBook

Demographic Items

- ID
 - alphanumeric format
- Age
 - Question text: Age
 - numeric format
- Gender
 - Question text: gender
 - Question text: Sex
 - Response Options:
 - 1 = Male
 - 2 = Female
 - 3= Binary
 - 4= Non-Binary
 - 5= I prefer not to answer
- Job
 - Question text: Job
 - Response Options:
 - 1= Self-employed worker, entrepreneur
 - 2= Freelancer / Liberal professional
 - 3= dependent worker
 - 4= Student
 - 5= Homemaker
 - 6= Unemployed, seeking first job
 - 7= Retired, property owner
- Edu
 - Question text: education level
 - Response Options:
 - 1 = Middle school or elementary school diploma
 - 2 = High school diploma
 - 3 = University degree or postgraduate degree
- PA_COMM

Question text: Do you belong to a parish community?

○ Response Options:

- 1 = Yes
- 2 = No

- SERV_COMM

Question text: Do you serve in the parish?

○ Response Options:

- 1 = Yes
- 2 = No

- SERV_DT

Question text: If yes, what service do you perform?

○ Response Options:

- 1= Parish priest
- 2= Deacon
- 3= Charity worker (Caritas Center, Listening Center, senior activities)
- 4= Altar server
- 5= Scout
- 6= Extraordinary minister
- 7= Catechist
- 8= Babysitting
- 9 = Other: _____

- SERV_TM

Question text: How long have you been serving?

○ Response Options:

- numeric format

Personality Inventory

Citation

Caci, B., Cardaci, M., Tabacchi, M. E., & Scrima, F. (2014). Personality variables as predictors of Facebook usage. *Psychological Reports, 114*(2), 528–539.

Measure Description

Personality traits, defined on the basis of the Big Five model, were measured using the Personality Inventory developed by Caci et al. (2014). The questionnaire contains 20 items and is inspired by the FFM test by Costa & McCrae (1992). Five subscales are included, each composed of four items related to a personality factor: Extraversion (E), Conscientiousness (C), Neuroticism (N), Openness (O), and Agreeableness (A). Responses to each item are based on a 5-point scale where 1 indicates “strongly disagree” and 5 indicates “strongly agree.”

Reverse		scored
1	=	5
2	=	4
3	=	3
4	=	2
5 = 1		

This is done using the formula $6 - \text{score}$, where 5 becomes 1.

Instructions

Please indicate, according to your personal opinion, how much you identify with the following statements. For each statement, please mark the appropriate number from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree).

Response options

- 1= strongly disagree
- 5= strongly agree

Items

- PI_1: I am rather emotionally stable.
- PI_2: I spend a lot of time just having fun.
- PI_3: I have a wide range of intellectual interests.
- PI_4: I am an irritable person.
- PI_5: I like having many people around me.

- PI_6: I like to take the lead in group activities.
- PI_7: I am a cheerful and lively person.
- PI_8: I would rather cooperate with others than compete with them.
- PI_9: I often enjoy playing with theories or abstract ideas.
- PI_10: I usually prefer to do things on my own.
- PI_11: I often feel helpless and want someone else to solve my problems.
- PI_12: I really enjoy talking with people.
- PI_13: I am more of a listener than a talker.
- PI_14: I work hard to accomplish my work.
- PI_15: I do not have a strong and dominant personality.
- PI_16: I like doing difficult tasks.
- PI_17: I experience a wide range of emotions and feelings.
- PI_18: I feel unable to handle many situations.
- PI_19: I do not like leaving anything unfinished.
- PI_20: I follow the same route when I go somewhere.

Subscale information

Openness: PI_3, PI_9, PI_17, PI_20,

Conscientiousness: PI_2, PI_16, PI_19, PI_14

Extraversion: PI_5, PI_7, PI_10, PI_12

Agreeableness: PI_6, PI_8, PI_13, PI_15

Neuroticism: PI_1, PI_4, PI_11, PI_18

Religious Orientation Scale Revised

Citation

Allport, G. W. (1950). *The individual and his religion*. New York: Macmillan

Allport, G. W., & Ross, J. M. (1967). Personal religious orientation and prejudice. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 5(4), 432.

Kirkpatrick, L. A., & Hood, R. W. (1990). Intrinsic-Extrinsic religious orientation: the boon or bane of contemporary psychology of religion? *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 29(4), 442.

Measure Description

The scale consists of 14 items, each of which can be assigned a score from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Items 1-3-4-5-7-10-12-14 refer to intrinsic religious orientation, items 2-11-13 refer to extrinsic–social religious orientation, and items 6-9 refer to extrinsic–personal religious orientation. Three items are reverse-scored: 3, 10, and 14. The score for each subscale is obtained by summing the corresponding items; the total ranges from 8 to 40 for the I (intrinsic) scale and from 3 to 15 for the E (extrinsic) scale.

Instructions

Please indicate, according to your personal opinion, how much you identify with the following statements. For each statement, please mark the appropriate number from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree).

Response options

- 1= strongly disagree
- 5= strongly agree

Items

- ROS_1: I enjoy reading about my religion
- ROS_2: I go to church because it helps me to make friends
- ROS_3: It doesn't much matter what I believe so long as i am good
- ROS_4: It is important to me to spend time in private thought and prayer
- ROS_5: I have often had a strong sense of God's presence
- ROS_6: I pray mainly to gain relief and protection
- ROS_7: I try hard to live all my life according to my religious beliefs

- ROS_8: What religion offers me most is comfort in times of trouble and sorrow
- ROS_9: Prayer is for peace and happiness
- ROS_10: Although i am religious, i don't let it affect my daily life
- ROS_11: I go to church mostly to spend time with my friends
- ROS_12: My whole approach to life is based on my religion
- ROS_13: I go to church mainly because I enjoy seeing people I know there
- ROS_14: Although i believe in my religion, many other things are more important in life

Subscale information

Extrinsic Personal Religious Orientation (ROS_EP): ROS_6, ROS_9

Extrinsic Social Religious Orientation (ROS_ES): ROS_2, ROS_11, ROS_13

Intrinsic Religious Orientation (ROS_I): ROS_1, ROS_3, ROS_4, ROS_5, ROS_7, ROS_10, ROS_12, ROS_14

Intrinsic Spirituality Scale

Citation

Hodge, D.R. (2003). The intrinsic spirituality scale: a new six items instrument for assessing the salience of spirituality as a motivational construct. *Journal of Social Service Research*, 30(1), 41-61.

Measure Description

Theistic spirituality was assessed using Hodge's (2003) Intrinsic Spirituality Scale. This scale includes 6 items consisting of questions to which participants respond using a Likert-type scale; individuals choose a statement associated with a number from 0 to 5. While 0 indicates an absence of spirituality, 5 refers to a high level of spirituality. The level of intrinsic spirituality is obtained by dividing the individual's total score by 6; a score of 0 indicates a person whose spirituality is not a motivating factor

Instructions

Please indicate, according to your personal opinion, how much you identify with the following statements. For each statement, please mark the appropriate number from 1 to 5.

Response options

- SPT_1: In terms of the questions i have about my life, spirituality answers...
1= no questions
5= absolutely all my questions
- SPT_2:
1= more important than anything else in my life
5= of no importance to me
- SPT_3:
1 = plays absolutely no role
5= is always the overriding consideration
- SPT_4:
1= not part of my life
5= the master motive of my life, directing every other aspect of my life
- SPT_5:
1= has no effect on my personal growth
5= is absolutely the most important factor in my persoal growth
- SPT_6:

1= no aspect of my life

5= absolutely every aspect of my life

Items

- SPT_1: In terms of the questions i have about my life, spirituality answers...
- SPT_2: Growing spirituality is...
- SPT_3: When i am faced with an important decision my spirituality...
- SPT_4: Spirituality is...
- SPT_5: When i think of the things that help me to grow and mature as a person, my spirituality...
- SPT_6: My spiritual beliefs affect...

Self-Report Altruism Scale

Citation

Manzur, E., & Olavarrieta, S. (2021). The 9-SRA Scale: a simplified 9- Items version of the SRA scale to assess altruism. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 6999.

Measure Description

Altruism was assessed using the Simplified 9-item version developed by Manzur & Olavarrieta (2021) of the Self-Report Altruism Scale by Rushton et al. (1981). The questionnaire consists of 9 items to which participants must assign a score from 1 (never) to 5 (always), based on how often they have performed the actions described in each item.

Instructions

Please indicate, according to your personal opinion, how frequently you have engaged in the following activities. For each statement, please mark the appropriate number from 1 (never) to 5 (always).

Response options

- 1= never
- 5= always

Items

- SRA_1: I have given money to a charity
- SRA_2: I have donated goods or clothes to a charity
- SRA_3: I have done volunteer work for charity
- SRA_4: I have helped carry a stranger's belongings
- SRA_5: I have made change for someone I did not know
- SRA_6: I have helped an acquaintance to move houses
- SRA_7: I have let a neighbor I did not know well borrow an item of some value to me
- SRA_8: I have offered to help a disabled or elderly stranger across a street
- SRA_9: I have offered my seat to a stranger who was standing

Altruism/Non altruism Scale

Citation

Śliwak, J. (2005). L'altruismo e la sua misurazione: questionario A/N. *Roczniki Psychologiczne*, 8 (1).

Śliwak, J., & Bartczuk, R. (2022). Altruism/Non-altruism Questionnaire– short version: The revision of the method based on bifactor analysis. *Journal for Perspectives of Economic Political and Social Integration*, 29(1), 31-59.

Measure Description

To assess the type of altruism enacted, the altruism/non-altruism questionnaire by Sliwak (2005) was used. The test includes vignettes depicting characters with whom participants can easily identify, as they are of the same sex and of an undefined age. The stories represent typical everyday situations in which an individual must help a person in difficulty, but doing so requires some sacrifice on the part of the helper. The possibility of receiving a reward for altruistic behavior is virtually nonexistent. The score of the AN scale corresponds to the sum of the scores from the two parts that make up the questionnaire. The first part consists of 9 stories and six response options representing varying degrees of altruistic behavior, while the second part consists of 8 stories. The total score ranges from 17 to 110; a lower score indicates a lack of altruistic behavior, whereas a higher score indicates stronger altruism. The description of the questionnaire can be found in Sliwak's article (2005, pp. 18–23), which provides instructions for administering the test and the stories to be read. In the first part, the author instructs participants to mark the letter corresponding to the behavior that, in their opinion, the character in the story would perform. In the second part, the author explains to the participant that they must evaluate, using a 6-point Likert scale—where 1 indicates “strongly agree” and 6 indicates “strongly disagree”—the behavior displayed by the protagonist of the story. Participants are asked to avoid, when possible, the response “I am not exactly in agreement.”

Instructions

From ALT_TYPE_1 to ALT_TYPE_9 : You will now be presented with some stories: please mark the box corresponding to the behavior that, in your opinion, the main character would carry out.

From ALT_TYPE_10 to ALT_TYPE_17 : You will now be presented with additional stories: please indicate how much you agree with the behavior displayed by the protagonist on a scale from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree).

Response options

From ALT_TYPE_1 to ALT_TYPE_9

ALT_TYPE_1

- He will refuse the loan
- He will hesitate for a long time but will eventually lend the money
- He will refuse the loan and also tell his friend not to contact him again for such matters
- After a long hesitation, he will refuse to give the loan
- He will lend the required amount and tell his friend that he can count on him in the future
- He will give the loan

ALT_TYPE_2

- He will not offer help
- He will hesitate for a long time, but will eventually offer help
- He will not offer help and will also make a critical remark about the person
- He will offer help
- After a long hesitation, he will not offer help
- He will offer help and even express willingness to help in the future

ALT_TYPE_3

- He will give up the ticket and also show concern for the situation
- He will hesitate for a long time and in the end will not give up the ticket
- He will give up the ticket
- He will not give up the ticket, will hold it up, and express indignation that someone dared to ask
- He will hesitate for a long time, but eventually will give up the ticket
- He will not give up the ticket

ALT_TYPE_4

- He will accept the neighbors' request and warmly welcome the cousin
- He will hesitate for a long time and in the end will not accept the neighbors' request
- He will accept the neighbors' request

- He will not accept the request and will even tell them how they could ask him something like this
- He will hesitate for a long time, but in the end will accept the neighbors' request
- He will not accept the neighbors' request

ALT_TYPE_5

- He will offer help and even express willingness to help in the future
- He will hesitate for a long time, and in the end will not offer help
- He will offer help
- He will not offer help and will add that the man should not bother others with his problems
- He will hesitate for a long time, but will eventually offer help
- He will not offer help

ALT_TYPE_6

- He will not accept the neighbor's request
- He will hesitate for a long time but will eventually accept the neighbor's request
- He will not accept the neighbor's request and will add that she should not contact him again for such matters
- He will hesitate for a long time and in the end will not accept the neighbor's request
- He will accept the neighbor's request
- He will accept the request and say he is also willing to help in similar situations in the future

ALT_TYPE_7

- She will refuse to help and will add that he should not contact her for such matters again
- She will hesitate for a long time but eventually help
- She will refuse to help
- She will hesitate for a long time and eventually refuse to help
- She will help him
- She will help him and declare her willingness to help in the future

ALT_TYPE_8

- He will not lend the book
- He will hesitate for a long time but eventually lend the book
- He will not lend the book and will say that everyone is looking for it, including himself

- He will hesitate for a long time and in the end will not lend the book
- He will lend the book
- He will lend the book and declare his willingness to help in similar situations in the future

ALT_TYPE_9

- She will not help
- She will hesitate for a long time but eventually help
- She will not help and will even tell her not to contact her again for such matters
- She will hesitate for a long time and in the end will not help
- She will help
- She will help and declare her willingness to assist in any future situation

From ALT_TYPE_10 to ALT_TYPE_17

- 1= completely disagree
- 5= completely agree

Items

- ALT_TYPE_1: Claudio's friend asks him to lend a sum of money. Claudio had planned to make larger purchases, which involve significant expenses that he would have to give up if he decided to help his friend. Claudio could make a sacrifice and postpone his planned expenses, but at the same time he knows he cannot rely on his friend's help in the future because the friend constantly has problems and needs help himself. What do you think Claudio will do?
- ALT_TYPE_2: Andrea has been discreetly observing for several minutes the person who works with him in the same room. This person, even though it's only the beginning of the day, looks tired, is unable to work, and would need help. If Andrea decides to help, he will have to stay longer at work. On the other hand, knowing this person, Andrea knows that his help will not be appreciated. What do you think Andrea will do?
- ALT_TYPE_3: Mimmo has been waiting in line for a long time to buy a ticket for a concert by his favorite band. He even skipped an appointment he was on his way to because he thought it would be nice to listen to some good live music. When his turn finally came, it turned out that he had bought the last ticket. He was happy that, even though the seat wasn't very good, at least the effort of standing in line and the time he had wasted were worth it. Suddenly, an unknown boy approaches Mimmo and asks him to sell the ticket, explaining that he had come from a very distant place with a group of friends who had previously ordered their tickets. The boy was sure he would manage to buy a ticket before the concert, but even though he arrived

early, he found out the line was so long that he couldn't get one. So he says he will have to spend the evening alone in an unfamiliar city, waiting for his friends. What do you think Mimmo will do?

- ALT_TYPE_4: Gregorio's neighbors have a cousin who is coming to visit them and will need to spend the night there for a few days. Their living conditions are difficult. There is a hotel nearby, and there are almost always free rooms, but it would be a big expense for the neighbors. So they turn to Gregorio and ask him to host the cousin for the night. Gregorio's situation is slightly better, but still not very comfortable, and accepting any stranger would cause him many problems and difficulties. At the same time, he knows that if he decides to host this cousin for the night, the neighbors will not appreciate his sacrifice. What do you think Gregorio will do?
- ALT_TYPE_5: Peter, while he was with his friends, met a man he had never met before. During the conversation that followed between them, Peter noticed that the person he was talking to was dealing with many problems that he could solve. Of course, addressing these issues would require sacrifices and a lot of precious time. Peter has many pending matters of his own and has known the man he is speaking with for only a few moments. What do you think Peter will do?
- ALT_TYPE_6: In the afternoon Paolo will go to his friend's birthday party. He is happy because he will meet friends and acquaintances he hasn't seen for a long time. It's nice to sit and have fun with people you care about. Shortly before leaving, a neighbor who knows nothing about his plans comes to Paolo and asks him to stay for a few hours with her small child, whom she can't leave anywhere, but she has a very important matter to take care of that she cannot postpone. Paolo is already ready for the event, and he would really love to go. If he stays with the child, he will miss the opportunity to have fun, and the neighbor will probably even forget to show him gratitude for it. What do you think Paolo will do?
- ALT_TYPE_7: Silvana worked hard today and finished her tasks early. She is getting ready to leave, but then a colleague approaches her — someone Silvana has worked with for a long time, although she has never had any contact with him outside the workplace. The colleague asks Silvana for help to finish a task because he can't manage it on his own. Silvana knows how to help him, but she just wants to leave as soon as possible. If she decides to help, she will have to stay even longer than usual. She knows her colleague well enough to know that he is not capable of appreciating anyone's help. What do you think Silvana will do?
- ALT_TYPE_8: Luca works and studies part-time. A few days ago, he managed to get a book that is hard to find and sought after by many people, which he needs to prepare for his exams.

So far Luca has only been able to briefly review the assigned material, because he has many other things to do. Today he was stopped on the street by a friend who, like him, studies part-time, but whom Luca only knows by sight. The friend he meets asks Luca for help in finding the book he is looking for, not knowing that Luca has this book. If Luca admits that he has the book and lends it to him, he won't have time to prepare properly, and the consequence could be failing the exam and having to take it again. What do you think Luca will do?

- ALT_TYPE_9: Giorgia recently came home from work after a very difficult day, so she decided not to do some household chores because she needs to rest. After some time, a neighbor—a woman living alone— comes to Giorgia and asks for help carrying a package to the post office because she cannot manage it on her own. Giorgia feels very tired and the post office is quite far away. What do you think Giorgia will do?
- ALT_TYPE_10: Marian is a person who smokes cigarettes. While he was leaving for a train trip, he decided to enter the smoking carriage. After about ten minutes, he took out a cigarette and lit it, but then he realized he was the only smoker in the carriage. The other passengers sitting in the smoking compartment did not complain, even though their faces clearly showed annoyance at the fact that Marian was smoking. Seeing this dissatisfaction, Marian quickly left, regardless of the fact that he was in the smoking carriage, because he believes that one should always consider the needs of other people. Do you agree with Marian's decision? About Marian's decision, you are:
- ALT_TYPE_11: Luca bought a lottery ticket and, to his great surprise, discovered that he had won a mobile phone. However, Luca already has a phone, so his intention is to sell the new one to make some money. On his way home, feeling happy, he remembered an advertisement in the newspaper saying that a retired man was looking for a mobile phone because his own had been stolen, and he lived in a remote area where a mobile phone was the only means of communication he had. Luca then reflected on the fact that the pensioner really needed a phone, but he couldn't expect any profit from him. So in the end he decided to sell the phone to someone else who would pay much more, because when someone is blessed with good luck, they should make the most of it. Do you agree with Luca's decision?
- ALT_TYPE_12: Giulio lives in an apartment building. Today, on his free Saturday, he has invited some guests over. Everyone is having a great time, and some people are a bit louder than others, but not too much. There is still time before 10:00 p.m. More than once, a neighbor comes to Giulio and asks him to get everyone to lower their voices because she would like to rest after work, and tomorrow, even though it's Sunday, she has to get up early. Giulio says that the neighbor probably has the right to rest, but he also has the right to enjoy himself at

home with his friends, especially because it is still a “decent” hour and he throws parties of this kind very rarely. So he decided not to quiet down his guests, because he had the right and the need to have fun. Do you agree with Giulio’s decision?

- ALT_TYPE_13: Luigi’s wife suggests visiting their friends who have invited them several times, and whom they haven’t visited in a long time. Luigi doesn’t like going to these friends’ house because their company tires and bores him. He would prefer to do something lighter at home that he enjoys and that allows him to rest afterward. However, if he refuses to go to the gathering, he will embarrass his wife, who enjoys visiting these friends and feels good there. After a brief reflection, Luigi decides that he would not go to visit them, because it would be too great a sacrifice for him and he must first take care of himself. Do you agree with Luigi’s decision?
- ALT_TYPE_14: Stefan, while traveling on the bus, is thinking about his problems, which have multiplied in recent days. His daydreaming is interrupted by a woman sitting next to him who, bored by the silence and motivated by the need to talk to someone, starts a conversation with Stefan — a conversation he is not willing to have, as he is tired and overwhelmed by his own problems. During the conversation, the unknown woman bores Stefan with things that seem so trivial that one would need “saintly” patience to listen to her. However, Stefan decides that he will not interrupt the conversation because the woman needs to express her frustration, and despite his own problems and tiredness, he will listen to her until the end with understanding and compassion, even going so far as to comfort her. Do you agree with Stefan?
- ALT_TYPE_15: Silvio is hurrying home from work as fast as he can, nervously checking his watch from time to time. He has arranged to meet a friend who was supposed to do something important for him, but if Silvio is late, the friend might not wait for him, and Silvio won’t see him again for about ten days or even longer. So he walks even faster when suddenly a boy on a bicycle riding on the sidewalk, hit by a distracted passerby, falls near Silvio. At first glance, it’s clear that nothing serious has happened to the boy, but he has started crying because he is surely hurt and frightened. Silvio wonders for a moment what he should do, because even though there are many people around, no one seems to show any interest in the crying boy. If he stops to comfort him, he will be late. However, he decides to stop because he cannot go on with his own matters — even the most important ones — when a crying boy needs help. Do you agree with Silvio’s decision?
- ALT_TYPE_16: Adam is relieved to think that the hard workday is over, that he has taken care of everything, and that, given today’s bad weather, he doesn’t have to leave the house. He is already waiting for the next episode of the series he is very interested in, which will

soon start on TV. Suddenly he hears the doorbell, opens the door, and sees an unknown man who says he is not from the area and asks for help in finding a doctor. Adam knows that the nearest doctor lives quite far away and that it will be difficult for a stranger to get there. For the man to reach his destination effectively, the best solution would be for Adam to go with him. However, thinking about the bad weather outside, his tiredness, and the show that is about to start, he decides to get rid of the man as quickly as possible, who does not know where the nearest doctor is. Do you agree with Adam's decision?

- ALT_TYPE_17: Michele has to walk at a faster pace to attend the last screening of a very interesting and widely discussed film that he hasn't had the opportunity to see before. The streets are almost empty, even though it isn't very late, because it's cold and raining. Michele is already close to the cinema when suddenly an elderly woman stops him and asks him to accompany her to the bus stop. Michele hesitates because if he walks slowly with the older woman, he will arrive late and miss his last chance to see the film, even though it means a lot to him. After thinking about it for a while, he decides that he must see the film, so he tells the woman that he cannot help her because he is in a hurry and walks away. Do you agree with Michele's decision?

